

A3a

A FAIR-enabling citation model for Cultural Heritage Objects

CHO Citation Elements. Repository Case Studies. Template

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A FAIR-enabling citation model for Cultural Heritage Objects

A3a / CHO Citation Elements. Repository Case Studies. Template

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Abstract

One of the activities of the project *A FAIR-enabling citation model for Cultural Heritage Objects* involved the in-depth analysis of citation practices of selected data repositories as case studies. To this end, a case study template was developed.

The template comprises several descriptors intended to identify the data repository and the repository data citation practices, along with one or more samples of citation records of objects, hosted by the repository, as use cases.

Version history

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List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
ARK	Archival Resource Key
CHO	Cultural Heritage Object
COAR	Confederation of Open Access Repositories
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PID	Persistent Identifier
PURL	Persistent Uniform Resource Locator
RDA	Research Data Alliance
ROR	Research Organization Registry
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
URN	Uniform Resource Name
VIAF	Virtual International Authority File

1 Introduction

One of the activities of the project *A FAIR-enabling citation model for Cultural Heritage Objects* involved the in-depth analysis of citation practices of some data repositories as case studies. A case study template was developed for this purpose.

The template comprises several descriptors intended to identify the studied data repository and the repository data citation practices, along with one or more examples of citation records of digital objects hosted by the repository as use cases.

2 Case Study Template

2.1 Rationale

Identify and label data repository descriptors involved in the analysis of a research data repository citation model.

2.2 Methodology

A descriptive model was developed to collect as much information as necessary for this purpose in order to better define a CHO citation model. The model aims to identify and label data repository descriptors involved in the analysis of a research data repository citation model.

To this end, [re3data.org](https://www.re3data.org/)¹ and [FAIRsharing.org](https://fairsharing.org/)² metadata schemas have been thoroughly analysed. Whenever possible, the data repository descriptors are elements drawn from the [re3data.org](https://www.re3data.org/) Metadata Schema 3.1³. Only the elements considered relevant for a FAIR data citation were taken into account.

The “Subjects” descriptor includes terms from the FAIRsharing Subject Ontology (SRAO)⁴.

Registries entries are used in the template elements values as much as possible. In particular, the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog⁵ for metadata standards, and [Bartoc.org](https://bartoc.org/)⁶ for semantic artefacts.

The identification of the data citation descriptors lays the foundation for an in-depth analysis of the citation practice in the reviewed data repository. Using some sample data objects, citation records can be presented and discussed, highlighting the strengths and weaknesses in terms of semantic reference to cultural heritage objects. Suggestions for improving the research data repository citation model can then be provided.

¹ <https://www.re3data.org/>

² <https://fairsharing.org/>

³ <https://doi.org/10.48440/re3.010>

⁴ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/ontologies/srao>

⁵ <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/>

⁶ <https://bartoc.org/>

2.3 Template

We use the namespace `r3d` = "<http://www.re3data.org/schema/3-1>" in the descriptors.

2.3.1 General

This section of the template aims at the identification of the data repository, and the description of the model and metadata of the digital objects it hosts.

Repository Name <i>r3d:repositoryName - The full name of the research data repository.</i>	E.g.: Phaidra - University of Padua
Repository URL <i>r3d:repositoryUrl - The URL of the research data repository.</i>	E.g.: https://phaidra.cab.unipd.it/
Repository identifier <i>r3d:repositoryIdentifier - A globally unique identifier that refers to the research data repository or a record describing the research data repository.</i> The URI of the research data repository identifier (DOI, ROR, RRID, Handle, etc.).	E.g.: https://doi.org/10.25430/phaidra
Repositories registry records The URLs of the research data repository record in the re3data.org , FAIRsharing.org , OpenDOAR repositories registry.	re3data.org: URL FAIRsharing.org: URL OpenDOAR: URL
Provider type <i>r3d:providerType - The type of provider.</i>	Data provider / Service provider
Data provider for aggregator/catalogue <i>The aggregator or catalogue services the research data repository provides the research data.</i> Catalogue/aggregator name and catalogue/aggregator home page URL, or Unknown.	E.g.: Europeana < https://www.europeana.eu > ARIADNE < https://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/ > OpenAIRE < https://www.openaire.eu/ >

	EOSC Marketplace and Portal < https://eosc-portal.eu/ >
Subjects <i>r3d:subject - The disciplinary focus of the research data repository.</i> Term from the FAIRsharing Subject Ontology or Other (provide related URL).	E.g.: Humanities and Social Science Art
Persistent identifier systems <i>r3d:pidSystem - The persistent identifier system that is used/provided by the research data repository for research data.</i> The PID systems provided by the research data repository: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DOI ● Handle ● ARK ● PURL ● URN ● Other (provide related URL) Provide also the registration authority (if known).	E.g.: ARK DOI (Datacite, Crossref, Medra) Handle
Policy <i>r3d:policy - Policies providing information concerning the usage of the research data repository.</i> The policy title and URL of the data curation policy, sustainability policy, data quality policy, etc. The data citation policy should be stated in the "Data Citation" section of the template.	E.g.: <i>Phaidra - University of Padua Preservation Plan</i> < https://bibliotecadigitale.cab.unipd.it/en/digital-library/digital-repositories/digital-preservation > DPLA Metadata Quality Guidelines < http://bit.ly/dpla-metadata-qual >
Repository certification <i>r3d:certificate - The certificate, accreditation or standard the research data repository complies with.</i>	E.g.: CoreTrustSeal < https://www.coretrustseal.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Phaidra-at-the-Library-System-of-the-University-of-Padova.pdf >, 2019

<p>The certificate name, URL, year of accreditation and validity period.</p>	
<p>Data model</p> <p>Brief description of the data model and/or related documentation URL.</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Phaidra data model is...</p> <p>https://phaidra.univie.ac.at/metadata-fields-help</p>
<p>Resource types</p> <p><i>r3d:contentType - All types of resources available in the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Term from COAR Resource Types Vocabulary 3.1.</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Image</p> <p>Sound</p> <p>Video</p> <p>Text</p> <p>Other (e.g. 3D Object)</p>
<p>Metadata standards</p> <p><i>r3d:metadataStandard - The metadata standard the research data repository complies with.</i></p> <p>Standard name and URI from the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog (preferable) or the Bartoc.org - Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications, or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Dublin Core <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/msc/m15></p> <p>MODS <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/msc/m97></p> <p>DataCite Metadata Schema <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/msc/m11></p> <p>CIDOC CRM <https://bartoc.org/en/node/1644></p>
<p>Object landing page metadata qualification</p> <p><i>Machine-readable metadata provided in the object landing page of the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Possible values:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schema.org • Dublin Core • EPrints metadata • Highwire Press metadata • Open Graph metadata • Signposting Typed Links • Other (provide related URL) 	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Schema.org</p> <p>Dublin Core</p> <p>Signposting Typed Links</p>

<p>Semantic artefacts integration</p> <p><i>The Semantic artefacts the research data repository supports in the object's metadata.</i></p> <p>The name of the semantic artefact and its URI (preferable: URI from Bartoc.org - Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications) or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>ORCID <https://bartoc.org/en/node/2021></p> <p>VIAF <http://bartoc.org/en/node/2053></p> <p>Wikidata QID <http://bartoc.org/en/node/1940></p> <p>Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus <http://bartoc.org/en/node/75></p>
<p>Versioning</p> <p><i>r3d:versioning - The research data repository supports versioning of research data.</i></p>	<p>Yes / No / Unknown</p>
<p>Data access rights</p> <p><i>r3d:dataAccessType - The access regulation to the research data sets provided by the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Term and URI from COAR Access Rights Vocabulary 1.1 or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>embargoed access <http://purl.org/coar/access_right/c_f1cf></p> <p>metadata only access <http://purl.org/coar/access_right/c_14cb></p> <p>open access <http://purl.org/coar/access_right/c_abf2></p> <p>restricted access <http://purl.org/coar/access_right/c_16ec></p>
<p>Data rights</p> <p><i>The applicable rights to the research data in the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Term and URI of data rights available in the research data repository from the RightsStatements.org list or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>In Copyright <http://rightsstatements.org/vocab/InC/1.0/></p> <p>In Copyright - Educational Use Permitted <http://rightsstatements.org/vocab/InC-EDU/1.0/></p>
<p>Data licences</p> <p><i>r3d:dataLicense - The license or licensing scheme the research data repository offers for research data.</i></p> <p>License name and URI from the SPDX Licence List or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-4.0.html></p> <p>Open Data Commons Attribution License v1.0 <https://spdx.org/licenses/ODC-By-1.0.html></p> <p>GNU General Public License v3.0 or later <https://spdx.org/licenses/GPL-3.0-or-later.html></p>

<p>Metadata licences</p> <p><i>The license or licensing scheme the research data repository offers for the research objects metadata.</i></p> <p>License name and URI from the SPDX License List or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Creative Commons Zero v1.0 Universal <https://spdx.org/licenses/CCo-1.0.html></p>
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Table 1: General section of the template.

2.3.2 Data Citation

This section aims at outlining the descriptors related to the citation-specific policies, features and citation model provided by the research data repository.

<p>Data citation policy</p> <p><i>r3d:citationGuidelineUrl - The URL of the policy outlining how to cite research data provided by the research data repository.</i></p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.rx91h486p</p>
<p>Endorsed data citation recommendations</p> <p><i>Data citation recommendations the repository endorses in the data citation policy.</i></p> <p>Data citation recommendation title and URL.</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Data Citation Synthesis Group: Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles. FORCE11 <https://doi.org/10.25490/a97f-egykh></p> <p>Heritage Data Reuse Charter <https://datacharter.hypotheses.org/></p> <p>CODATA-ICSTI Task Group on Data Citation Standards and Practices, "Out of Cite, Out of Mind: The Current State of Practice, Policy, and Technology for the Citation of Data" <https://www.jstage.jst.go.jp/article/dsj/12/0/12_OSOM13-043/_pdf></p>
<p>"Cite as" feature</p> <p><i>An automatic feature the research data repository provides in order to cite the research data.</i></p>	<p>Yes / No / Unknown</p>
<p>Data citation styles</p> <p><i>The citation styles the research data repository provides in order to cite the research data.</i></p> <p>Available citation styles in the "Cite as" feature of the research data repository, and the citation style tools implemented (e.g. Citation Style Language processor "citeproc-js").</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>APA, MLA, Chicago - via citeproc-js CSL processor.</p>
<p>Data citation record elements</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Title [Mandatory]</p>

<p><i>Critical citation elements provided in the data citation record of the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Citation element and citation element property in the citation record.</p>	<p>Creator [Mandatory]</p> <p>PID [Mandatory]</p> <p>Publisher [Optional]</p>
<p>Data citation record syntax</p> <p><i>The data citation record format the research data repository provides to cite the research data.</i></p> <p>The element names comprised in the data citation record in the format and order the research data repository provides.</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Creator (Publication Date) Title, Publisher, Distributor Name [Distributor], Depositing Institution Name [Depositing Institution]. DOI</p>
<p>Data citation record semantics</p> <p><i>The Semantic artefact elements provided in the data citation record of the research data repository.</i></p> <p>The name of the semantic artefact and its URI (preferable: URI from Bartoc.org - Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications) or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>ORCID <https://bartoc.org/en/node/2021></p> <p>VIAF <http://bartoc.org/en/node/2053></p> <p>Wikidata QID <http://bartoc.org/en/node/1940></p> <p>Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus <http://bartoc.org/en/node/75></p>

Table 2: Data Citation section of the template.

2.3.3 Use case

Analysis of the citation record of a selected digital object. It also comprises an automated FAIRness assessment of the digital object. This section is intended to be duplicated for each analysed digital object.

<p>Use case name</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Adults and Lifelong Learning</p>
<p>Example object</p> <p><i>The example object to review.</i></p> <p>The URL of the example object (PID preferable).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.9S16DS12F</p>
<p>Resource type</p> <p>Term from COAR Resource Types Vocabulary 3.1 or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Image</p> <p>Video</p>
<p>Object type</p> <p>Term from Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Scores <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300026427></p> <p>Sound recordings <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300028633></p>
<p>Automated FAIRness assessment</p> <p><i>The FAIRness assessment of the research object provided by an automated FAIR data assessment tool.</i></p> <p>Score and URL of the automated FAIRness assessment achieved in the F-UJI FAIR Data Assessment tool.</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>60 %, https://f-uji.net/view/422 (F-UJI 2.2.5)</p>
<p>Automated citation metadata</p> <p><i>The object metadata retrieved by an automated citation tool.</i></p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>https://v4e-lab.isti.cnr.it/citview/demo/index.html?schema_url=https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.9S16DS12F</p>

<p>The URL of the automated citation metadata retrieved by the Citation Metadata Viewer Demo tool.</p>	
<p>Citation record</p> <p><i>The citation record provided by the research data repository.</i></p> <p>The default citation record of the example object.</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>National Museum of Ireland. (2019) Adults and Lifelong Learning, Digital Repository of Ireland [Distributor], Arts and Culture in Education Research Repository [Depositing Institution], https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.9s16ds12f</p>

Table 3: Use case section of the template.

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